

Viewpoint for ES&T 60th Anniversary Facet on Persistence

The Pedagogical Case for More Diversity in Thinking About PMT Contaminants

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I am fairly sure that it was a talk by Don Mackay at the 1999 SETAC North America meeting when I first realized that persistence and mobility were regarded by some as essential characteristics of chemical contaminants that are important or interesting. Having spent the beginning of my career studying contaminant transformation reactions with half-lives of minutes to hours, I felt the need for a more inclusive perspective. On the flight home, I sketched the figure described below and found it very helpful for exercising my thinking about the issue. Since then, I have found the rubric represented by this figure to be a very useful heuristic for teaching, but I was not sure about its value in research or regulatory contexts. However, while participating in planning for the “Facet of Impact” on Persistence for ES&T’s 60th anniversary,¹ I found myself referring back to the figure repeatedly, so I decided this would be a good time to try the rubric on a wider audience.

The basic idea of **Figure 1** will be obvious immediately. However, as soon as one tries to apply it, the pedagogical implications quickly become apparent. To start, why label the axes transformation and transport and not persistence and mobility? I chose *transformation* rather than *persistence* because the former term precisely and literally refers to any reactivity that converts a parent compound to daughter products, whereas the latter term is complicated by definitions that include reaction and partitioning in multiple phases (i.e., overall persistence²), series of reactions involving parent and daughter products (i.e., joint or secondary persistence^{3,4}), or are limited by association with the widespread operational definition of lacking reactivity in a standard assay (e.g., ready biodegradability^{5,6}). Similarly, the horizontal axis is labeled *transport* rather than *mobility* because the former simply refers to any movement of a contaminant through or between any media, whereas the latter can be complicated by more sophisticated definitions (e.g., spatial range⁷) or limited by association with partitioning-focused operational definitions that are used in screening and ranking of chemical contaminants for regulation.^{6,8-10} I think these choices make the resulting TT rubric (**Figure 1**) more general than the standard PM framework,⁵ in part

because the former allows more flexibility in assigning the endpoints for each axis (as exemplified below). In addition, the TT framework is not necessarily environmental, so it is more applicable to other fields such as chemical engineering, occupational health, or toxicology.

Figure 1. Rubric for classification of environmental contaminants along continua for transformation (recalcitrant to labile) and transport (immobile to mobile). (A) Four quadrants labelled with abbreviations for end-member characteristics. (B) Corners labeled with prototypical examples of each end-member and selected examples for each quadrant. C-4 is the plastic explosive (mostly RDX), OC is oleoresin capsicum (pepper spray), CS is in tear gas.

Obviously, both axes represent continua. However, to facilitate further discussion, I have drawn and labelled quadrants in **Figure 1A** using RM for recalcitrant & mobile, LI for labile & immobile, etc. In **Figure 1B**, I have assigned a prototypical example to each corner and listed other prominent examples in each quadrant. In part because we prioritize thinking about persistent organic pollutants,^{11, 12} most of the examples shown in the RI and RM quadrants will be familiar, even to most students. The most famous persistent organic pollutants (the Stockholm Convention POPs: DDT, PCBs, etc.) are not shown because they are RI as soil/sediment contaminants but RM from the perspective of long-range atmospheric fate. In contrast to the familiarity of most POPs, contaminants that go away quickly (i.e., are readily degraded or dispersed) get relatively less attention, so it is less obvious what the prototypical examples should be for quadrants LI and LM. To maintain the focus on organic contaminants for now, I have chosen TNT (when deployed as a solid in munitions) and VX (the nerve agent) for LI and LM, respectively.

Now we can test the heuristic value of the TT rubric by using it to classify other contaminants. Some emerging contaminants clearly belong in the RM quadrant—such as metformin, 1,4-dioxane, methyl tert-butyl ether (MTBE), 1,2,3-trichloropropane (TCP), and other persistent and mobile organic compounds (PMOCs¹³)—but many others exhibit “intermediate persistence”, where the contaminant’s fate is highly contingent on “confounding factors” (i.e., environmental or test conditions).¹² Examples from this group include most pharmaceutical and personal care products, pesticides, and surfactants. Other categories of mobile organic contaminants that are more or less labile to transformation depending on context are the disinfection byproducts (DBPs), including NDMA, and tire-wear derived compounds such as 6PPD and 6PPDQ.¹⁴ Larger and more complex organic molecules—such as the toxic natural products microcystin and ricin—might be best classified as intermediate with respect to their persistence and mobility. Some organic contaminants are regulated as solid-phase mixtures (e.g., creosote, coal tar), which would make them RI, except insofar as they undergo dissolution into individual chemical components, most of which are moderately mobile and labile. Considerable effort has gone into developing (semi)quantitative metrics for persistence^{10, 15} that could be used to plot these contaminants on **Figure 1**. However, versions of that analysis have been done before,^{15, 16} and the main goals of this viewpoint are better served by diversifying beyond the application domain of those models.

The most obvious category of contaminants to add to our scope is metals, including heavy metal cations and metal(loid) oxyanions. Metals can be regulated in a manner analogous to organics,¹⁷ but the role of transformation and transport for these contaminants must be considered differently because they are so closely coupled. Most metals are subject to transformation among species (depending on Eh, pH, etc.), and this speciation can result in high mobility or indefinite sequestration. For example, the Cr(VI) oxyanion is mobile in groundwater, whereas the Cr(III) cation precipitates as a rather insoluble oxyhydroxide. Thus, total Cr defines a diagonal in **Figure 1** that runs from LM for Cr(VI) to RI for Cr(III). Notably, the diagonal is reversed for arsenic, with As(III) being LM and As(V) being RI. In both cases, despite the complications due to their speciation reactions, the total metal is conserved (i.e., persistent), which is consistent with the consensus that these are important environmental contaminants.

Applying the TT rubric to some non-metal inorganic contaminants is straightforward: clearly, perchlorate and fluoride belong in the RM quadrant and ozone and chlorine are LM. White phosphorus (P₄) is a non-metal inorganic and pyrophoric solid used in munitions,¹⁸ making it an extreme example of an LI contaminant. However, classifying the non-metal oxyanion nitrate requires consideration of the source scenario. Nitrate certainly is mobile and labile to transformation, but its concentration in environmental media often is maintained by sustained release from various sources, making it “pseudo-persistent”. The classification of contaminants as pseudo-persistent is debatable within the PM framework,^{11, 19} but in the TT rubric nitrate clearly belongs in the LM quadrant.

Until now, I have avoided explicitly addressing toxicity, but just as it is usually included with PM (as PMT), it could be applied similarly to TT (i.e., TTT). With PMT, the focus is on contaminants with considerable toxicity, but the diversity of the contaminant types considered here using the TT rubric introduces more diversity in toxicological effects. So, if the primary mode of toxicity for each contaminant group were encoded into Figure 1, it would show that the recalcitrant contaminants are mainly associated with chronic toxicity, whereas the labile contaminants tend to be acutely toxic. This contrast is only evident because of the broader diversity of contaminants accommodated by the TT rubric. This distinction is important because chronic toxicity endpoints are not necessarily more important than acute endpoints, especially from the perspective of human health. The TT rubric might even be useful in understanding the environmental fate and transport of substances that are natural and/or without significant toxicity, such as the biogeochemical cycling of N, P, or S.

When I teach using this figure, I challenge the students to apply it not only to chemicals, but to all types of contaminants that might be of environmental concern. This includes contaminants that are radiological, material (colloids, nanoparticles, fibers), and biological (bacteria, viruses, protozoa, prions). Some are easy to classify—for example, students have no trouble assigning radon to the RM quadrant—but classifying materials such as carbon nanotubes, microplastics, asbestos, and PM_{2.5} requires consideration of how particle morphology influences transformation and transport (and toxicity). Also challenging to think about are materials composed of metals that are subject to corrosion and passivation, such as lead, iron, and silver, the form of which can range from pipes to nanoparticles.

The category of biological contaminants might seem non sequitur at first, but if we generalize transformation to include from living to dead (rather than just parent to daughter), then the TT rubric is applicable. For example, it could be helpful to recognize that *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and spore-forming species like *Cryptosporidium* are RM contaminants (via air and water, respectively), SARS-CoV-2 is LM (via air), prions are RI, and HIV is LI (immobile in the sense that their only mode of transfer is direct contact). One could even repurpose the z-axis for toxicity, in this case using semi-quantitative metrics for virulence.²⁰ I have found that public health students find this analogy between pathogens and other types of contaminants to be especially illuminating and engaging; and yet I think many others would consider it to be out-of-scope for the PMT framework.

Recently, I have further expanded the outline of contaminant types covered in my courses to include the energy contaminants heat, light, and noise. Their significance to overall human, environmental, and planetary health is arguably just as important as the chemical and material contaminants discussed above, but would applying the TT rubric provide any insight into this? All of the energy contaminants are highly labile to transformation (to lesser forms of energy) and their mobility ranges from high (heat) to very high (light). So, these contaminants all belong in the LM quadrant, except insofar as they are subject to continuous resupply, which would make them pseudo-persistent, as discussed above for nitrate. While this application of the TT rubric to energy contaminants is meant to be a bit provocative, the students and half-dozen colleagues that beta-tested this viewpoint all seemed to find the resulting discussion worthwhile.

The intent of this viewpoint is not to engage in debate over the sufficiency of using PMT metrics to prioritize contaminants for regulation,^{12, 21-24} or to counter the consensus that persistent contaminants deserve special attention under the precautionary principle.¹¹ Rather, the point is to demonstrate that putting PMT thinking into a broader context that includes a more diverse range of contaminant types reveals cases where contaminants that are not persistent and/or mobile are still important and interesting. Furthermore, as a pedagogical exercise, working with the TT(T) rubric can be used to stimulate thinking beyond familiar categories of chemical contaminants and to compare the fate, effects, and associated risks of all environmental stressors.

Associated Content

Supporting Information

Several versions of Figure 1 are provided as Supporting Information to facilitate use by others.

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Notes

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